

Mitochondrial metabolism: Yin and Yang for tumor progression

Lorea Valcarcel-Jimenez^{1,*}, Edoardo Gaude^{2,*}, Veronica Torrano^{1,3,*} Christian Frezza^{2,6#} and
Arkaitz Carracedo^{1,3,4,5,6,#}

¹CIC bioGUNE, Bizkaia Technology Park, 801a bld., 48160 Derio, Bizkaia, Spain

²MRC Cancer Unit, University of Cambridge, Hutchison/MRC Research Centre, Box 197,
Cambridge Biomedical Campus, Cambridge, CB2 0XZ, United Kingdom

³ CIBERONC

⁴Ikerbasque, Basque foundation for science, 48011 Bilbao, Spain

⁵Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Department, University of the Basque Country
(UPV/EHU), P. O. Box 644, E-48080 Bilbao, Spain.

⁶Correspondence to:

Arkaitz Carracedo, acarracedo@cicbiogune.es

Christian Frezza, cf366@MRC-CU.cam.ac.uk

* Equal contribution

#: co-corresponding authors

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21 **Altered metabolism is a distinct feature of cancer cells. During transformation, the**
22 **entire metabolic network is rewired to efficiently convert nutrients to biosynthetic**
23 **precursors to sustain cancer cell growth and proliferation. Whilst the molecular**
24 **underpinnings of this metabolic reprogramming have been described, its role in tumor**
25 **progression is still under investigation. Importantly, the mitochondria is a central actor**
26 **in many of the metabolic processes that are altered in tumors. Yet, we have only begun**
27 **to understand the dualities of mitochondrial function during cancer metastasis and**
28 **therapy resistance. Paradoxically, mitochondrial metabolism can be both**
29 **advantageous and detrimental to these processes, highlighting the need for a better**
30 **understanding of the molecular and micro-environmental cues that define the role of**
31 **this fascinating organelle. In this review article, we present an updated view on the**
32 **different mitochondrial metabolic strategies adopted by cancer cells to overcome the**
33 **many hurdles faced during tumor progression.**

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36 Introduction

37 Cancer is a multifaceted disease whose pathogenesis remains elusive, despite the series of
38 breakthroughs since the discovery of the first oncogene, *SRC*, more than 50 years ago (see
39 **glossary**) [1]. Although it was initially thought that a set of mutations in specific oncogenes
40 and tumor suppressors was sufficient to drive tumorigenesis, the spontaneous accumulation
41 of such mutations in otherwise healthy tissue [2] indicates that cell transformation is a process
42 exceeding this initial simplistic view. Indeed, tumorigenesis is supported by acquisition of cell-
43 and non-cell-autonomous traits, known as the hallmarks of cancer [3]. Among these, altered
44 energy metabolism has recently gained some attention. Bolstered by the development of a
45 variety of techniques to assess the cellular metabolome, it has been shown that during
46 transformation cancer cells undergo profound metabolic changes, including activation of
47 glycolysis, altered utilization of amino acids, and dysregulation of mitochondrial function [4].
48 The availability of large-scale datasets from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA,
49 <https://cancergenome.nih.gov/>) has allowed the identification of the underpinning genetic
50 determinants of these metabolic changes, showing that they are orchestrated by well-known
51 oncogenes and tumor suppressors [5]. Furthermore, it has been observed that tumors share
52 a subset of metabolic gene signatures independent of their tissue of origin, and upregulate
53 genes that encode for glycolysis and nucleotide biosynthesis enzymes [6, 7]. On the other
54 hand, recent experiments using elegant mouse models showed that cancers also retain
55 metabolic features from their tissue of origin [8].

56 Mitochondria co-ordinate a large fraction of metabolic, energetic, and physiological
57 processes, and their integrity is a central checkpoint for cancer cells [4]. In this respect, the
58 finding that genetic alterations of mitochondrial metabolic enzymes, such as Fumarate
59 Hydratase (FH), Succinate Dehydrogenase (SDH), and Isocitrate Dehydrogenase (IDH1/2)
60 [9], can predispose or contribute to cancer shook the field. In fact, investigations on these
61 models revealed that metabolites of mitochondrial origin accumulated in these tumors can
62 activate oncogenic signaling cascades, making them *bona fide* oncometabolites [9]. In

63 addition to exacerbated or inhibited metabolite production, cancer cells also exploit the
64 reversible nature of many metabolic reactions. In fact, beyond aberrant activation of glycolysis,
65 the use of the tricarboxylic acid cycle in reversed mode (reductive carboxylation) enables the
66 use of glutamine for biosynthetic purposes in cells with dysfunctional mitochondria [10, 11].
67 Interestingly, a compilation of experimental evidence suggest that mitochondrial dysfunction
68 can reach a threshold where it turns from advantageous to detrimental for cancer cells. In this
69 line, depletion of mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) upon disruption of the mitochondrial
70 transcription factor A (TFAM) inhibits mutant *Kras*-driven tumorigenesis in mice [12].
71 Furthermore, mtDNA-depleted cancer cells transplanted in mice acquire whole mitochondria
72 from host cells via horizontal transfer as a strategy to restore their mitochondrial function
73 [13]. These results indicate that changes in mitochondrial metabolism are not only mere
74 consequences of transformation and that fine regulation of mitochondrial function is required
75 to drive tumorigenesis.

76 While the metabolic underpinnings of tumor initiation have been described for a wide range
77 of tumor types, little is known on the metabolic adaptations that can occur at later phases of
78 cancer progression. The aim of this review article is to focus on the initial evidence gathered
79 in recent years about the role of mitochondrial metabolism during the stages following cancer
80 initiation and accompanying cancer progression. Understanding how tumor cells rewire and
81 adapt their mitochondrial metabolism during tumor progression could be instrumental both for
82 the development of novel anticancer strategies and for the identification of aggressiveness
83 signs of prognostic value

84

85 **Altered mitochondrial metabolism contributes to tumor progression**

86 The importance of metabolism in cancer is illustrated by the fact that tumors can be clustered
87 based on their metabolic signature, with important implications for cancer diagnosis and
88 patient stratification [7]. However, tumors are far from being a static entity. Environmental

89 constraints, such as nutrient and oxygen availability, and the exposure to anti-tumor agents,
90 inevitably challenge the survival of cancer cells and force their evolution and/or selection within
91 the tumor [14]. Indeed, recent evidence indicates that the metabolic phenotype of cancer
92 varies at different disease stages, and it is a contributing factor for tumor progression (**Figure**
93 **1**). For instance, an increase in glycolytic enzymes and a decrease in mitochondrial
94 transcriptional programs has been observed at different stages of prostate cancer progression
95 [15, 16]. Similarly, stage-specific metabolic traits were identified in breast [17], renal cancer
96 [18], and lung cancer [19]. In this context, mitochondrial metabolism seems to play a key role.
97 Transcriptional analysis of 21 tumor types collected by the TCGA revealed that the repression
98 of genes related to mitochondrial metabolism is strikingly associated with poor clinical
99 outcome and is associated with the presence of an epithelial to mesenchymal transition (EMT)
100 gene signature, a molecular pathway linked to tumor initiation, invasion, and metastasis [24].
101 These results suggest that during tumor progression, mitochondrial dysfunction can be
102 advantageous and could make cancer cells more motile and invasive, predisposing to
103 metastasis. Complementary studies have showed that mutations of enzymes from the TCA
104 cycle ,SDH and FH, are linked to the activation of EMT and invasive phenotype in
105 pheochromocytoma and paraganglioma [25] and renal cancer [26]. Similarly, mtDNA
106 abundance displays high heterogeneity among human tumors and mtDNA depletion, which is
107 generally associated with bioenergetics defects, is linked with poor patient prognosis in
108 several human cancers [27].

109 Overall, these results indicate that the suppression of TCA cycle enzymes provides a
110 distinct advantage to the cancer cells during tumor progression, and it can contribute to the
111 clinical outcome of patients. However, there are also reported examples of mitochondrial
112 dysfunction being detrimental for cancer aggressiveness. Studies performed on renal
113 oncocytoma, a benign tumor characterized by aberrant accumulation of dysfunctional
114 mitochondria, showed that defects in mitochondrial function can inhibit the autophagic
115 machinery, thus creating a metabolic checkpoint that inhibits tumor progression [20].

116 Conversely, activation of autophagy is fundamental to support mutant *Ras*-driven cancer cells
117 by providing substrates for mitochondrial metabolism and clearing dysfunctional mitochondria
118 [21-23]. Consistently, inhibition of autophagy leads to mitochondrial dysfunction and blocks
119 malignant tumor progression by reprogramming tumor fate towards benign neoplasms [21].

120 With this new perspective of mitochondrial function as friend and foe for tumor
121 progression, it will be important to define in future studies to which extent is this phenomenon
122 the consequence of tissue or tumor-specific mitochondrial requirements. Alternatively, it could
123 be the result of a byphasic contribution of this organelle to tumour progression, being the
124 reduction in mitochondrial function progressively advantageous to cancer cells until it reaches
125 a “minimal integrity point”, below which this alteration becomes detrimental.

126 **The dual role of mitochondrial metabolism in cancer cell dissemination and metastasis**

127 During tumor progression, epithelial cells face loss of anchorage to their native location, which
128 triggers a stress response that leads to cell death in a process termed anoikis [28]. The bypass
129 of this phenomenon requires a profound adaptation of cellular metabolism, which has been
130 reviewed elsewhere [29]. In addition, once detached, cancer cells remain exposed to
131 additional micro-environmental stresses in their journey to a foreign distant tissue to establish
132 metastatic lesions. These challenges include the invasion beyond the basal membrane,
133 intravasation (with the potential requirement of EMT), survival in circulation, extravasation,
134 homing in a secondary organ and tumor regrowth [30] (**Figure 2**). This process is
135 tremendously inefficient as the majority of maladapted cells die in circulation or upon reaching
136 a hostile microenvironment. Yet, a small percentage of cells with intrinsic abilities or sufficient
137 plasticity to adapt and survive upon intravasation can successfully colonize a secondary organ
138 [30]. Once seeded, cancer cells re-enter a proliferative stage (a process that can take from
139 weeks to years) and overcome the hostile environmental conditions to generate a
140 disseminated tumor. Importantly, these cells will need to optimize their metabolic state

141 according to the characteristics of the target tissue, as well as to their own mutational
142 background.

143 The determinants of the metabolic adaptations during dissemination and metastasis are
144 only partially known. In line with the increase in oxidative stress during anchorage-
145 independent growth [28, 31], it was recently shown that metastatic cells from primary
146 melanoma require the activation of mitochondrial antioxidant pathways to survive [32]. In
147 support of these findings, it was recently shown that cell detachment leads to a complex
148 rewiring of nutrient utilization, with reductive carboxylation being a key pathway to generate
149 antioxidant molecules [33, 34]. Overall, cancer cells that detach from the primary tumor
150 experience oxidative stress and, by activating antioxidant pathways, they can overcome this
151 challenge and eventually metastasize. This view is supported by the many examples with
152 isolated antioxidant genes or chronic therapies with antioxidant properties that promote
153 metastasis [35-41].

154 The activation of specific transcriptional programs that regulate mitochondrial activity
155 during cancer cell dissemination and metastasis underpins these metabolic changes. In
156 prostate cancer, active mitochondrial oxidative metabolism represents a disadvantageous
157 metabolic state for cancer cells and leads to tumor suppression [16]. Moreover, deletion of the
158 master transcriptional regulator of mitochondrial oxidative metabolism, Peroxisome
159 proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1 alpha (PGC1 α), in the mouse prostate
160 induces a glycolytic switch and promotes cancer progression and metastasis, in agreement
161 with the down-regulation of PGC1 α observed in human specimens [16]. Of note, striking
162 similarities exist between prostate cancer specimens that will eventually recur and the
163 metastatic lesions, in terms of the PGC1 α -dependent metabolic program. These results
164 suggest that the selection process for metabolically fit metastatic clones could start in primary
165 tumors long before prostate cancer disseminates (**Figure 2**). Interestingly, in a complementary
166 study in melanoma it was shown that PGC1 α suppresses metastasis through the regulation
167 of an adhesion and invasion transcriptional program [42]. In support of a role of mitochondrial

168 dysfunction in promoting metastasis, partial inhibition of mitochondrial respiratory chain with
169 rotenone is sufficient to induce cell migration and clonogenicity *in vitro* and to support lung
170 metastasis *in vivo* [43]. Finally, mtDNA mutations affecting complex I have been found to
171 support breast cancer metastasis *in vivo* via de-regulation of NAD⁺/NADH and activation of
172 autophagy. Importantly, rescue of mitochondrial function through enhancement of complex I
173 activity could inhibit formation of metastasis[44].

174 Despite these consistent lines of evidence, the role of mitochondrial function in metastasis
175 remains controversial. For instance, increased mitochondrial function was detected in
176 circulating cells from orthotopically-implanted breast cancer [45], suggesting that tumor-
177 specific reprogramming might occur during metastasis. The same study showed that
178 establishment of metastases was accompanied by decrease expression of OXPHOS genes,
179 thus adding complexity to the role of mitochondrial function in the survival of matrix-detached
180 cells and distant tissue colonization [45]. Of note, differential use of pyruvate in the
181 mitochondria has been recently shown to dictate the site of metastasis in breast cancer [46,
182 47]. Breast-cancer-derived lung metastases showed increase dependency on pyruvate
183 conversion into oxaloacetate through Pyruvate Carboxylase activation [46]. Liver-metastatic
184 cells, however, divert pyruvate into lactate production as a result of increased activity of
185 Pyruvate Dehydrogenase Kinase 1 [47]. These results suggest that metastatic cells undergo
186 adaptations that are dictated by the different metabolic landscapes of target tissues and call
187 for a careful analysis of metastatic site-dependent metabolic rewiring.

188 Changes in mitochondrial function are inherently linked with the increased requirement of
189 antioxidant molecules of disseminated cells that we described above. Multiple strategies can
190 be adopted to increase antioxidant power (**Figure 2**). On the one hand, a decrease in
191 mitochondrial activity would result in reduced production of mitochondrial free radicals. This is
192 the proposed mechanism in melanoma [32], where cells activate compensatory antioxidant
193 mechanisms (folate metabolism, the main producer of reducing power [48]). On the other
194 hand, activation of PGC1 α pathway would result in increased mitochondrial metabolism and

195 activation of an antioxidant program, which would counteract oxidative stress. This strategy is
196 observed in breast cancer [45], and is in line with other studies pointing at the enhanced
197 antioxidant response activated upon induction of PGC1 α [49]. Therefore, cancer cells with
198 different genetic drivers or tissue-of-origin constraints might differ in the optimal metabolic state
199 that counteracts oxidative stress and supports the sequential process of metastasis. Finally,
200 a recent study highlighted the link between epigenetic changes occurring in PDAC metastases
201 and reprogramming of the oxidative branch of the pentose phosphate pathway [50], thus
202 indicating that epigenetic mechanisms might control the antioxidant capacity of metastatic
203 cells. Overall, these studies increase the complexity of the oncogenic activity of metabolic
204 programs and call for caution when defining a dogmatic and static oncogenic metabolic
205 reprogramming.

206 **Metabolic adaptation contributes to therapy resistance**

207 As discussed above, the ability to adapt the metabolic phenotype at different stages of the
208 disease is a clear advantage for cancer cells. This metabolic modulation is also key when
209 cancer cells are subject to the toxic effects of anticancer drugs. Indeed, specific metabolic
210 features of cancer cells can overcome the toxic effects of anticancer drugs, leading to
211 chemoresistance [51-57] or support lipid synthesis and mutagenesis in these challenging
212 conditions [58] (**Figure 3**). For instance, cisplatin resistance is driven by a metabolic
213 reprogramming that supports the generation of antioxidant molecules, including NADPH via
214 the pentose phosphate pathway [51] and glutathione biosynthesis from glutamine [53].
215 Resistance to oncogene addiction [55] has been also shown to rely on metabolic adaptation.
216 In this model, the extinction of mutant *KRas* in established tumors leads to the selection of a
217 subpopulation of resistant cells dependent on mitochondrial metabolism [55]. Similar findings
218 have been made in melanoma, in which inhibition of B Raf^{V600} in B Raf^{V600} -driven melanoma
219 induces an oxidative phosphorylation switch orchestrated by PGC1 α [49, 52], enhancing the
220 detoxification capacities of these cells. In addition, resistance to MAPK inhibitors in this type
221 of cancer is associated with increase mitochondrial DNA content and oxidative

222 phosphorylation [57]. These results are in support of a role of activated mitochondrial function
223 as a key determinant of therapy resistance (**Figure 3**).

224 Of note, core cellular processes such as genomic integrity pathways and cell cycle
225 progression are tightly associated to mitochondrial function. On the one hand, mitochondrial
226 dysfunction is accompanied by depletion of nucleotide pools and this has been linked with the
227 induction of DNA damage [59]. Beyond the well-established role of DNA damage in eliciting
228 genome instability and support tumorigenesis, high mutational burden has been linked to
229 increased sensitivity to the checkpoint inhibitors anti-CTLA-4 [60] and anti-PD1 [61]. On the
230 other hand, cell cycle checkpoint regulators Cyclin D3-CDK6 negatively regulate mitochondrial
231 metabolism by drifting glucose-derived carbons away from the TCA and into the pentose-
232 phosphate pathway, hence supporting the production of antioxidant power [62]. This profound
233 interplay between mitochondrial metabolism and core cellular checkpoints reveals the
234 potential of targeting the activity of this organelle in combination therapies to harness the
235 vulnerabilities of tumor cells.

236 Mitochondrial metabolism is heterogeneous within and between tumors [63], as evidenced
237 in studies on cancer stem cell biology and antiangiogenic therapies [64-67]. These results
238 suggest that the efficacy of anticancer therapy may depend on the intrinsic metabolic features
239 of cancer cells. It also supports the notion that cancer cells endowed with higher adaptive
240 metabolic capacity, or benefiting from the metabolic support of the microenvironment [68] can
241 more easily escape drug toxicity. Furthermore, due to the association of cancer-initiating and
242 therapy-resistant cells to a more oxidative metabolic program, it is tempting to speculate that:
243 i) the emergence of therapy-resistant cancer clones relies on the newly acquired metabolic
244 state, and ii) this metabolic plasticity can be therapeutically exploited through the combination
245 of standard and anti-metabolic therapies (**Figure 3**).

246

247 **Concluding Remarks**

248 Metabolic rewiring is a hallmark of cancer. Well-characterized changes in mitochondrial
249 metabolism generally provide a growth advantage in an environment that supports cell
250 proliferation. However, this program needs to be complemented by additional metabolic
251 strategies to support anchorage-independent growth, metastatic dissemination, or
252 pharmacological challenges. In this scenario, mutations in oncogenes and tumor suppressors
253 can be seen as ways to reach new metabolic landscapes. Given that this metabolic
254 reprogramming is tissue-specific, cancer cells might need to activate different gene networks
255 depending on their tissue of origin. This hypothesis could explain why most of the well-
256 characterized oncogenes and tumor suppressors exhibit potent regulatory functions on the
257 metabolic network, and why they are selected in specific tissues. The benefit of specific
258 mitochondrial metabolic features at different stages of tumor progression and in response to
259 therapy are yet to be clarified. Interestingly, changes in metabolism are frequently associated
260 to epigenetic alterations through transcriptional or post-translational modifications, rather than
261 irreversible genomic events. It is therefore possible that a specific metabolic landscape would
262 enable epigenetic flexibility to control gene expression.

263 Finally, although these metabolic adaptations might provide a selective advantage to
264 cancer cells, they will likely unveil novel therapeutic vulnerabilities. Restricting the metabolic
265 modulation of cancer cells and cornering them into a specific metabolic state, either by
266 pharmacological strategies or changing nutrient availability, could be a strategy to hamper
267 tumor progression and increase therapeutic efficacy. Understanding the different metabolic
268 states that cancer cells can acquire upon therapeutic treatment is therefore crucial for the
269 development of successful anticancer strategies.

270

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284 **References**

- 285 1. Martin, G.S. (2001) The hunting of the Src. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2 (6), 467-475.
286 2. Martincorena, I. and Campbell, P.J. (2015) Somatic mutation in cancer and normal cells.
287 *Science* 349 (6255), 1483-9.
288 3. Hanahan, D. and Weinberg, R.A. (2011) Hallmarks of cancer: the next generation. *Cell* 144
289 (5), 646-74.
290 4. Pavlova, N.N. and Thompson, C.B. (2016) The Emerging Hallmarks of Cancer Metabolism.
291 *Cell Metab* 23 (1), 27-47.
292 5. Cairns, R.A. et al. (2011) Regulation of cancer cell metabolism. *Nat Rev Cancer* 11 (2), 85-
293 95.
294 6. Hu, J. et al. (2013) Heterogeneity of tumor-induced gene expression changes in the human
295 metabolic network. *Nat Biotechnol* 31 (6), 522-9.
296 7. Gaude, E. and Frezza, C. (2016) Tissue-specific and convergent metabolic transformation
297 of cancer correlates with metastatic potential and patient survival. *Nat Commun* 7, 13041.
298 8. Mayers, J.R. et al. (2016) Tissue of origin dictates branched-chain amino acid metabolism
299 in mutant Kras-driven cancers. *Science* 353 (6304), 1161-5.
300 9. Sullivan, L.B. et al. (2016) Altered metabolite levels in cancer: implications for tumour
301 biology and cancer therapy. *Nat Rev Cancer* 16 (11), 680-693.
302 10. Mullen, A.R. et al. (2014) Oxidation of alpha-ketoglutarate is required for reductive
303 carboxylation in cancer cells with mitochondrial defects. *Cell Rep* 7 (5), 1679-90.
304 11. Mullen, A.R. et al. (2011) Reductive carboxylation supports growth in tumour cells with
305 defective mitochondria. *Nature* 481 (7381), 385-8.
306 12. Weinberg, F. et al. (2010) Mitochondrial metabolism and ROS generation are essential for
307 Kras-mediated tumorigenicity. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 107 (19), 8788-93.
308 13. Dong, L.F. et al. (2017) Horizontal transfer of whole mitochondria restores tumorigenic
309 potential in mitochondrial DNA-deficient cancer cells. *Elife* 6.
310 14. Lipinski, K.A. et al. Cancer Evolution and the Limits of Predictability in Precision Cancer
311 Medicine. *Trends in Cancer* 2 (1), 49-63.
312 15. Pertega-Gomes, N. et al. (2015) A glycolytic phenotype is associated with prostate cancer
313 progression and aggressiveness: a role for monocarboxylate transporters as metabolic targets
314 for therapy. *J Pathol* 236 (4), 517-30.
315 16. Torrano, V. et al. (2016) The metabolic co-regulator PGC1alpha suppresses prostate
316 cancer metastasis. *Nat Cell Biol* 18 (6), 645-56.
317 17. Denkert, C. et al. (2012) Metabolomics of human breast cancer: new approaches for tumor
318 typing and biomarker discovery. *Genome Medicine* 4 (4), 37-37.
319 18. Hakimi, A.A. et al. (2016) An Integrated Metabolic Atlas of Clear Cell Renal Cell
320 Carcinoma. *Cancer Cell* 29 (1), 104-16.
321 19. Kerr, E.M. et al. (2016) Mutant Kras copy number defines metabolic reprogramming and
322 therapeutic susceptibilities. *Nature* 531 (7592), 110-3.
323 20. Joshi, S. et al. (2015) The Genomic Landscape of Renal Oncocytoma Identifies a
324 Metabolic Barrier to Tumorigenesis. *Cell Rep* 13 (9), 1895-908.
325 21. Guo, J.Y. et al. (2011) Activated Ras requires autophagy to maintain oxidative metabolism
326 and tumorigenesis. *Genes Dev* 25 (5), 460-70.
327 22. Guo, J.Y. et al. (2013) Autophagy suppresses progression of K-ras-induced lung tumors
328 to oncocytomas and maintains lipid homeostasis. *Genes Dev* 27 (13), 1447-61.
329 23. Guo, J.Y. et al. (2016) Autophagy provides metabolic substrates to maintain energy charge
330 and nucleotide pools in Ras-driven lung cancer cells. *Genes Dev* 30 (15), 1704-17.
331 24. Nieto, M.A. et al. (2016) EMT: 2016. *Cell* 166 (1), 21-45.
332 25. Lorient, C. et al. (2012) Epithelial to mesenchymal transition is activated in metastatic
333 pheochromocytomas and paragangliomas caused by SDHB gene mutations. *J Clin Endocrinol*
334 *Metab* 97 (6), E954-62.
335 26. Sciacovelli, M. et al. (2016) Fumarate is an epigenetic modifier that elicits epithelial-to-
336 mesenchymal transition. *Nature* 537 (7621), 544-547.

337 27. Reznik, E. et al. (2016) Mitochondrial DNA copy number variation across human cancers.
338 Elife 5.
339 28. Schafer, Z.T. et al. (2009) Antioxidant and oncogene rescue of metabolic defects caused
340 by loss of matrix attachment. *Nature* 461 (7260), 109-13.
341 29. Carracedo, A. et al. (2013) Cancer metabolism: fatty acid oxidation in the limelight. *Nat*
342 *Rev Cancer* 13 (4), 227-32.
343 30. Massague, J. and Obenauf, A.C. (2016) Metastatic colonization by circulating tumour cells.
344 *Nature* 529 (7586), 298-306.
345 31. Jeon, S.M. et al. (2012) AMPK regulates NADPH homeostasis to promote tumour cell
346 survival during energy stress. *Nature* 485 (7400), 661-5.
347 32. Piskounova, E. et al. (2015) Oxidative stress inhibits distant metastasis by human
348 melanoma cells. *Nature* 527 (7577), 186-91.
349 33. Jiang, L. et al. (2014) Reductive carboxylation mediated oxidative stress defense supports
350 anchorage independent cell growth. *Cancer & Metabolism* 2 (Suppl 1), P30-P30.
351 34. Jiang, L. et al. (2016) Reductive carboxylation supports redox homeostasis during
352 anchorage-independent growth. *Nature* 532 (7598), 255-8.
353 35. Chen, E.I. et al. (2007) Adaptation of energy metabolism in breast cancer brain
354 metastases. *Cancer Res* 67 (4), 1472-86.
355 36. Dey, S. et al. (2015) ATF4-dependent induction of heme oxygenase 1 prevents anoikis
356 and promotes metastasis. *J Clin Invest* 125 (7), 2592-608.
357 37. Kamarajugadda, S. et al. (2013) Manganese superoxide dismutase promotes anoikis
358 resistance and tumor metastasis. *Cell Death Dis* 4, e504.
359 38. Lu, X. et al. (2010) Metabolomic changes accompanying transformation and acquisition of
360 metastatic potential in a syngeneic mouse mammary tumor model. *J Biol Chem* 285 (13),
361 9317-21.
362 39. Qu, Y. et al. (2011) Thioredoxin-like 2 regulates human cancer cell growth and metastasis
363 via redox homeostasis and NF-kappaB signaling. *J Clin Invest* 121 (1), 212-25.
364 40. Wang, H. et al. (2016) NRF2 activation by antioxidant antidiabetic agents accelerates
365 tumor metastasis. *Sci Transl Med* 8 (334), 334ra51.
366 41. Le Gal, K. et al. (2015) Antioxidants can increase melanoma metastasis in mice. *Sci Transl*
367 *Med* 7 (308), 308re8.
368 42. Luo, C. et al. (2016) A PGC1 α -mediated transcriptional axis suppresses melanoma
369 metastasis. *Nature* 537 (7620), 422-426.
370 43. Porporato, P.E. et al. (2014) A mitochondrial switch promotes tumor metastasis. *Cell Rep*
371 8 (3), 754-66.
372 44. Santidrian, A.F. et al. (2013) Mitochondrial complex I activity and NAD⁺/NADH balance
373 regulate breast cancer progression. *J Clin Invest* 123 (3), 1068-81.
374 45. LeBleu, V.S. et al. (2014) PGC-1 α mediates mitochondrial biogenesis and oxidative
375 phosphorylation in cancer cells to promote metastasis. *Nat Cell Biol* 16 (10), 992-1003, 1-15.
376 46. Christen, S. et al. (2016) Breast Cancer-Derived Lung Metastases Show Increased
377 Pyruvate Carboxylase-Dependent Anaplerosis. *Cell Rep* 17 (3), 837-848.
378 47. Dupuy, F. et al. (2015) PDK1-Dependent Metabolic Reprogramming Dictates Metastatic
379 Potential in Breast Cancer. *Cell Metab* 22 (4), 577-89.
380 48. Fan, J. et al. (2014) Quantitative flux analysis reveals folate-dependent NADPH
381 production. *Nature* 510 (7504), 298-302.
382 49. Vazquez, F. et al. (2013) PGC1 α expression defines a subset of human melanoma
383 tumors with increased mitochondrial capacity and resistance to oxidative stress. *Cancer Cell*
384 23 (3), 287-301.
385 50. McDonald, O.G. et al. (2017) Epigenomic reprogramming during pancreatic cancer
386 progression links anabolic glucose metabolism to distant metastasis. *Nat Genet*.
387 51. Catanzaro, D. et al. (2015) Inhibition of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase sensitizes
388 cisplatin-resistant cells to death. *Oncotarget* 6 (30), 30102-14.
389 52. Haq, R. et al. (2013) Oncogenic BRAF regulates oxidative metabolism via PGC1 α and
390 MITF. *Cancer Cell* 23 (3), 302-15.

391 53. Hudson, C.D. et al. (2016) Altered glutamine metabolism in platinum resistant ovarian
392 cancer. *Oncotarget* 7 (27), 41637-41649.

393 54. Samatar, A.A. and Poulikakos, P.I. (2014) Targeting RAS-ERK signalling in cancer:
394 promises and challenges. *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 13 (12), 928-942.

395 55. Viale, A. et al. (2014) Oncogene ablation-resistant pancreatic cancer cells depend on
396 mitochondrial function. *Nature* 514 (7524), 628-32.

397 56. Ying, H. et al. (2012) Oncogenic Kras Maintains Pancreatic Tumors through Regulation of
398 Anabolic Glucose Metabolism. *Cell* 149 (3), 656-670.

399 57. Zhang, G. et al. (2016) Targeting mitochondrial biogenesis to overcome drug resistance
400 to MAPK inhibitors. *J Clin Invest* 126 (5), 1834-56.

401 58. Havas, K.M. et al. (2017) Metabolic shifts in residual breast cancer drive tumor recurrence.
402 *J Clin Invest*.

403 59. Mannava, S. et al. (2013) Depletion of deoxyribonucleotide pools is an endogenous source
404 of DNA damage in cells undergoing oncogene-induced senescence. *Am J Pathol* 182 (1),
405 142-51.

406 60. Snyder, A. et al. (2014) Genetic basis for clinical response to CTLA-4 blockade in
407 melanoma. *N Engl J Med* 371 (23), 2189-99.

408 61. Rizvi, N.A. et al. (2015) Cancer immunology. Mutational landscape determines sensitivity
409 to PD-1 blockade in non-small cell lung cancer. *Science* 348 (6230), 124-8.

410 62. Wang, H. et al. (2017) The metabolic function of cyclin D3-CDK6 kinase in cancer cell
411 survival. *Nature* 546 (7658), 426-430.

412 63. Hensley, C.T. et al. (2016) Metabolic Heterogeneity in Human Lung Tumors. *Cell* 164 (4),
413 681-94.

414 64. Sancho, P. et al. (2015) MYC/PGC-1alpha Balance Determines the Metabolic Phenotype
415 and Plasticity of Pancreatic Cancer Stem Cells. *Cell Metab* 22 (4), 590-605.

416 65. Allen, E. et al. (2016) Metabolic Symbiosis Enables Adaptive Resistance to Anti-
417 angiogenic Therapy that Is Dependent on mTOR Signaling. *Cell Rep* 15 (6), 1144-60.

418 66. Jimenez-Valerio, G. et al. (2016) Resistance to Antiangiogenic Therapies by Metabolic
419 Symbiosis in Renal Cell Carcinoma PDX Models and Patients. *Cell Rep* 15 (6), 1134-43.

420 67. Pisarsky, L. et al. (2016) Targeting Metabolic Symbiosis to Overcome Resistance to Anti-
421 angiogenic Therapy. *Cell Rep* 15 (6), 1161-74.

422 68. Gui, D.Y. et al. (2016) Environment Dictates Dependence on Mitochondrial Complex I for
423 NAD⁺ and Aspartate Production and Determines Cancer Cell Sensitivity to Metformin. *Cell*
424 *Metab* 24 (5), 716-727.

425

426 **Figure legends**

427

428 **Figure 1. Metabolic adaptations during cancer progression.** Schematic representation of
429 the evolution and progression of cancer, based on specific metabolic rewiring. Upon the
430 establishment of an initial tumor mass, the acquisition of additional genetic mutations can lead
431 to metabolic changes that will confer cancer cells different proliferative/survival capabilities.
432 Survival of cancer cells and subsequent tumor progression is dependent on the acquisition of
433 a successful metabolic state, defined here as metabolic flexibility. Please note that genetic
434 mutations have been depicted as single consecutive events for simplicity, but various
435 cumulative mutations can occur at each stage.

436

437 **Figure 2. Metabolic modulation during metastatic dissemination.**

438 Schematic representation of the stages of metastatic dissemination (proliferation,
439 dissemination and metastasis). Right panel provides a summary of the metabolic adaptation
440 exhibited by different tumor types and the estimated exposure to reactive oxygen species
441 (ROS). *, glycolytic activity is presumed from results indicating reduced mitochondrial mass
442 **, glycolytic activity is presumed from the progressive decrease in mitochondrial oxidative
443 transcriptional programs from primary to metastatic cells. References: 1- Piskounova E. et al.,
444 Nature 2015; 2- Torrano V. et al., Nature Cell Biology 2016; 3- Le Bleu V.S. et al., Nature Cell
445 Biology 2014; 4- Dupuy F. et al., Cell Metabolism 2015). Met: Metastasis.

446

447 **Figure 3. Metabolic modulation as a phenomenon underpinning therapy resistance.**

448 Schematic representation of how metabolic adaptations can enable resistance to anticancer
449 therapies. The acquisition of drug resistance induces new metabolic essentialities that can be
450 harnessed to specifically target resistant cells.

451

452 GLOSSARY

453 **Metastasis** The process whereby, during tumor progression, cancer cells can leave the
454 primary tumor mass and disseminate to other tissues and organs. Metastasis to vital organs
455 is considered the main cause of death for cancer patients.

456

457 **Mitochondria** Intracellular organelles at the core of cell metabolism involved in the coupling
458 of oxygen consumption and nutrient catabolism to produce energy and metabolic
459 intermediates for the cell. These are the sites where OXPHOS and TCA cycle occur.

460

461 **Metabolism** It is the set of life-sustaining chemical reactions/transformations that occur
462 within the cells of living organisms.

463

464 **Metabolic adaptation** The intrinsic ability of the network of metabolic reactions to
465 adapt to external stimuli (e.g. nutrient availability, pharmacological treatment) or internal
466 alterations (e.g. mutations) in order to maintain cell homeostasis. Metabolic adaptation can
467 allow to quickly change cellular phenotype and function.

468

469 **EMT** Epithelial-to-Mesenchymal Transition; a process in which epithelial cells loss
470 adhesion properties and become mesenchymal cells with invasive and migratory capacities.

471

472 **FH** Fumarate Hydratase; mitochondrial enzyme that catalyzes the reversible
473 hydration/dehydration of fumarate to malate in the TCA cycle.

474

475 **MtDNA** Mitochondrial DNA

476

477 **OXPHOS** Oxidative Phosphorylation; metabolic pathway that occurs in the mitochondria
478 in which nutrients are oxidized releasing energy that is then converted into ATP.

479

480 **PC** Pyruvate Carboxylase; an enzyme that catalyzes the irreversible carboxylation
481 of pyruvate to oxaloacetate (OAA).

482

483 **PDAC** Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma.

484

485 **PGC1 α** Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ co-activator 1 α ; a transcriptional
486 co-factor implicated in energy metabolism and the principal regulator of mitochondrial
487 biogenesis.

488

489 **SDHA** Succinate Dehydrogenase A; Subunit of the succinate-ubiquinone
490 oxidoreductase as part of the mitochondrial respiratory chain. Contains the FAD binding site
491 where succinate is deprotonated and converted to fumarate.

492

493 **SRC** Proto-Oncogene Tyrosine-Protein Kinase.

494

495 **TCA** Tricarboxylic acid; Series of biochemical reactions used by all aerobic
496 organisms to release energy (ATP) through oxidation of nutrients.

497

498 **TCGA** The Cancer Genome Atlas.

499